

DIRECTIVE LANGUAGE AND POLITENESS NORMS IN HIGH SCHOOL TEACHER-STUDENT EXCHANGES

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Abstract

Background: Language politeness plays a crucial role in daily interactions, including those within educational context. This study examines the politeness of directive speech acts in communication between teachers and students at one high school in Jember Regency, Indonesia, focusing on the forms of speech acts, the level of politeness, the factors that influence them, and their impact on communication effectiveness.

Materials and Methods: This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach with observation, interview, listening and writing techniques. Data were obtained from direct observation inside and outside the classroom, interviews with four teachers and students, and analysis of conversation transcripts and supporting literature. Results: The study indicate that teachers apply a variety of directive speech acts strategically. Direct commands are used for academic instruction and discipline enforcement, while indirect commands are used more to motivate students and maintain politeness. Politeness strategies are realized through personal greetings, choosing polite diction, and adjusting intonation according to the classroom context. The level of politeness in communication is influenced by various factors, including the teacher's educational background, language habits, classroom dynamics, emotional closeness, individual characteristics of teachers and students, emotional conditions during interactions, and cultural and linguistic influences. Conclusion: The findings of this study underline the importance of implementing politeness in directive speech acts to create effective and harmonious communication in the school environment. The use of adaptive communication strategies not only increases the effectiveness of learning but also strengthens the educational relationship between teachers and students. The implications of this study can be a reference for educators in optimizing classroom interactions by considering the principles of language politeness.

Keywords: directive speech acts; linguistic study; politeness of language; teacher-student communication

Introduction

Communication between teachers and students in the learning process has a dual function, namely as a means of conveying knowledge, as well as a medium for forming student character. Devito¹ emphasizes the importance of effective information exchange, as well as how teachers must be able to control the messages conveyed so that learning objectives can be achieved. In this case, good communication includes not only the delivery of learning materials but also the method of delivery, which must be adjusted to social norms, ethics, and values of politeness.

Speech act theory by Austin in Rosyida & Siroj² explains that "every verbal communication contains a certain intention called a speech act, which is divided into three aspects: locution (what is said), illocution (the intention contained in the utterance), and perlocution (the effect produced by the utterance)". In the school environment, especially when teachers give instructions or directions, the speech acts that often appear are directive speech acts. Directive speech acts include requests, orders, or instructions that aim to influence the behavior of the interlocutor, in this case, students.

It is important to remember that in giving directions or orders, teachers need to pay attention to the aspect of politeness so that the interaction remains harmonious and does not cause any resistance from students. Politeness, according to the theory of politeness put forward by Tsalis³, is "a strategy used by speakers to maintain the "face" of the interlocutor, which is divided into two: positive face (the desire to be accepted and appreciated) and negative face (the desire not to be disturbed and maintain freedom)". In communication between teachers and students, teachers must be able to maintain a balance between giving clear instructions and still respecting the autonomy and dignity of students.

The use of politeness in directive speech acts by teachers can show respect for student independence, while also maintaining authority as educators. If teachers deliver instructions in an overly authoritative manner without paying attention to aspects of politeness, this has the potential to cause resistance from students and create a less conducive classroom atmosphere. Conversely, when teachers are able to provide direction in a polite and empathetic manner, students tend to respond more positively, feel respected and are more motivated to follow the instructions given⁴.

Afriansyah et al.⁵ stated that politeness also has a cultural aspect that influences an individual's communication style. In Indonesia, as a country that highly values politeness and manners, the use of polite language in everyday communication, including in educational environments, is something that is expected. Teachers, as figures who have authority in schools, have a responsibility not only to deliver lesson materials but also to be role models in instilling politeness values and language ethics in students. Thus, the way teachers provide direction or instructions to students must always consider the norms of politeness that apply in society.

At the high school level, students are at an important developmental stage, where they begin to form independence and personal identity. At this stage, students tend to be more sensitive to how they are treated by adults, including teachers. Therefore, politeness in delivering directions becomes increasingly important, because it not only affects students' understanding of instructions but also affects the interpersonal relationship between teachers and students. Interactions that are full of respect and politeness can strengthen the emotional bond between teachers and students and support the creation of a conducive learning environment⁶.

This study uses the theory of speech acts and politeness. Austin⁷ was the first to introduce the term speech act. He argued that language activity is not only limited to expressing something but also includes actions taken based on the statement. This opinion is reinforced by Austin and Searle⁸ which states that the

smallest unit in communication is not a sentence but rather certain actions, such as making statements, questions, commands and requests.

Regarding speech, Austin⁷ classifies speech acts into three categories: locutionary speech acts, illocutionary speech acts, and perlocutionary speech acts. This study focuses on the illocutionary speech acts used by teachers in teaching and learning activities.

Illocutionary speech act is a speech act that carry out certain actions concerning to the delivery of information. The action can be promising, commanding, or apologizing expressed through speech⁹. For example, in the speech:

"I'm not going."

The utterance occurred on Sunday when the speaker called his interlocutor, who was in the rain. The speaker had promised to go out with his interlocutor but delivered the utterance that is not only as a notification but also as an apology for the cancellation of the promise. The information conveyed by the speaker was less significant, considering that it was likely that his interlocutor could not go either due to the same weather conditions.

Austin & Searle⁸ divided the illocutionary act into three parts as follows:

a. Assertive Speech Acts

Assertive speech acts are illocutionary acts in which the speaker is bound to the truth of the proposition expressed, for example through statements, proposals, or reports. An example of an assertive speech act is: "How about we go to Lombok for vacation this year?" This utterance is a suggestion from the speaker to inform his/her conversation partner about beautiful tourist destinations.

b. Directive Speech Acts

Directive speech acts aim to produce an effect in the form of an action carried out by the speech partner (this illocutionary act is referred to by Leech as an impositive illocutionary speech act), for example ordering, commanding, requesting, or recommending.

c. Commissive Speech Acts

A commissive speech act is an illocution in which the speaker is bound to an action in the future, such as in a promise or offer. An example of a commissive speech act is: "What do you want to buy for your little brother when you start working?" This utterance contains an offer that shows the speaker's commitment to act in the future.

Meanwhile, the theory of politeness used in this study is Leech's theory of politeness. Leech¹⁰ emphasized that politeness in educational communication is very important to maintain a harmonious relationship between teachers and students. In the context of directive speech acts, politeness not only functions to create a conducive learning atmosphere but also contributes to the development of a relationship of mutual respect between the two parties. This is in line with Brown's view¹¹ which states that politeness is a way to protect one's 'face' in social interactions. By using polite and respectful language, teachers help students feel valued and supported, which in turn increases their motivation to learn.

The use of politeness in directive speech acts has a crucial role in creating effective communication between teachers and students. In this context, the theory of politeness proposed by Brown¹¹ is also relevant to consider. According to them, politeness serves to protect the individual's 'face' in social interactions. In this case, the face of students as the party interacted with by the teacher needs to be maintained through the use of polite language. Thus, when teachers speak using polite speech acts, they indirectly give appreciation to students, which can increase students' self-confidence and motivation to learn.

This study took data from one of the leading senior high schools in Jember Regency, East Java, Indonesia, which is known to have a disciplined educational environment and is oriented towards building student character. As an institution that emphasizes academic and ethical values, interaction between teachers and students is an important aspect in building a conducive learning culture. In this context, communication between teachers and students is not only aimed at delivering lesson materials but also reflects aspects of character building, one of which is through politeness in communication.

Politeness in communication is an important aspect in educational interactions, especially in the relationship between teachers and students. Directive speech acts, which include commands, requests, invitations, prohibitions, and suggestions, are one of the dominant forms of communication in school learning. However, politeness in these speech acts is not only influenced by linguistic norms but also by cultural factors and technological developments that shape interaction patterns in the school environment. This school has a strong local cultural background, which is reflected in the norms of politeness of the local community. As part of the Tapal Kuda region, the distinctive Madurese and Javanese cultures also shape the way students and teachers communicate. This culture is known for its respectful attitude towards elders and the use of language that tends to be hierarchical, which influences politeness strategies in directive speech acts in the classroom. Teachers at this school generally prioritize a persuasive approach and maintain interpersonal relationships in giving instructions, while students show respect through the choice of more subtle and indirect words.

In addition to cultural factors, the use of technology in learning also affects communication patterns between teachers and students. With the existence of digital learning platforms, such as WhatsApp class groups and Learning Management Systems (LMS), interactions not only take place directly in the classroom but also through online media. This technology allows teachers to convey directions more flexibly, while students have more time to formulate more polite responses in written communication. However, on the other hand, technology-based communication can also reduce nonverbal aspects that play a role in building politeness, thus creating challenges in maintaining polite communication norms.

There are several studies examining speech acts in the school environment. First was research by Ningsih¹² which focused on the analysis of politeness strategies used by high school teachers in communicating with students. This study found that the use of polite directive speech acts can increase students' acceptance of teacher instructions and create a more harmonious learning atmosphere. Furthermore, Putra¹³ through

his research examined the types of directive speech acts such as commands, requests, and prohibitions used by Indonesian language teachers in junior high schools. The results showed that although teachers used direct speech acts more often, they still maintained politeness through subtle and considered word choices. Research by Nugroho & Sari¹⁴ examined politeness strategies in imperative speech, in high schools in Bandung city, focusing on how age and social status factors influence teachers' language style. The results of the study showed that politeness strategies in giving orders can make instructions easier for students to accept.

Other research by Prisantiningtyas & Aulia¹⁵ studied the context of communication in online classes at a vocation school and found that virtual interactions tend to be more polite and adhere to the principles of politeness in language. Research by Suherman & Gani¹⁶ focused their study on the use of directive politeness strategies by Indonesian language teachers in 11th grade of high school. The results showed that there were 4 directive speaking strategies used by teachers, namely (1) speaking frankly without small talk, (2) speaking frankly with positive politeness, (3) speaking frankly with negative politeness, and (4) speaking vaguely. The speech act most frequently used by teachers was the directive speech act of demanding. Meanwhile, the directive speech act that was used least was directive speech act suggests.

Recent research by Rahmawati¹⁷ emphasized the importance of politeness strategies in the context of digital learning. Using a discourse analysis approach, this study revealed that the use of command mitigation through polite language was able to maintain harmony and effectiveness of communication even though it occurred in a limited digital space.

Based on a study of several previous studies on politeness in teacher and student interactions, it appears that most of the studies still focus on politeness strategies used by teachers, as shown in Ningsih's¹², Nugroho & Sari's¹⁴, and Suherman & Gani's¹⁶. Although there is a mention of the role of students in maintaining politeness, in-depth analysis of the politeness strategies used by students themselves is still rare. The focus of previous research also tends to be limited to directive speech acts, such as orders, requests, and prohibitions, as studied by Putra¹³ and Nugroho and Sari¹⁴, while other types of speech acts such as representative, expressive, or declarative have not been widely studied in the context of education. These studies are also generally conducted in the context of formal learning, especially Indonesian language subjects, without examining forms of politeness in non-formal learning interactions or other subjects that have different communication characteristics.

Most studies only focus on junior high school and senior high school levels and are conducted in certain areas such as Bandung City, so they are less representative of geographical variations and other levels of education. Prisantiningtyas & Aulia's¹⁵ and Rahmawati's¹⁷ have begun to study politeness in online communication, but their focus is still limited to mitigation strategies in commands without reaching broader aspects such as digital etiquette, the communication devices used, and the influence of local socio-cultural dynamics on politeness practices in virtual spaces.

Research on politeness in directive speech acts in high school is important to understand the extent of the effectiveness of the application of the principles of politeness in speech acts between teachers and students. Therefore, the focus of this study is to identify, analyze, and evaluate the politeness of directive speech acts between teachers and students. Thus, researchers are interested in discussing the politeness of directive speech acts in teacher and student communication at school.

Material and Methods

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach to examine the application of politeness in directive speech acts in communication between teachers and students at one high school in Jember Regency, Indonesia. According to Moleong¹⁸, qualitative research is a research approach that focuses on an in-depth understanding of social phenomena or human behavior in a natural context. In contrast to quantitative research, which emphasizes more on numerical measurement and analysis, qualitative research collects data in descriptive form, such as interviews, observations, or documents, to explore the perspectives, experiences, and meanings given by the research subjects. The main purpose of qualitative research is to understand the processes, reasons, and patterns that exist in the phenomena studied, by providing a richer and more comprehensive picture of the context.

The types of data in this study are divided into primary data and secondary data. The primary data type was obtained through direct surveys using the observation and writing technique when conducting observations and conducting interviews with recording techniques at the research location. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from literature studies that are in accordance with this study. The data sources used in this study were the results of interviews with 4 teachers and 4 students regarding perception in communicating.

Data collection using triangulation techniques of data sources and methods. Triangulation techniques in this study are used as a technique for combining all data and data sources to carry out checks received. In this study, triangulation was carried out by comparing the results of interviews, observations and documentation to ensure the consistency and validity of the findings obtained. Triangulation, operationally, in this study was carried out to ensure the validity and reliability of data through the combination of various sources and data collection methods. This triangulation is carried out in two forms, namely triangulation of source and triangulation of method. In this study, triangulation of source was conducted by collecting data from various informants through interviews, observations, and documentation. Meanwhile, in triangulation of method, researchers combine various methods, such as interviews, observations, and documentation, to obtain more complete and valid data. By implementing triangulation of method, researchers can increase the credibility of research results, for each method used complements each other and provides a different perspective on the phenomenon being studied.

Result

Directive speech acts used

Based on the results of observations with Interviewee 1, a teacher, it was found that the forms of directive speech acts used in communication between teachers and students are very diverse. According to Puspitari¹⁹, "directive speech acts are speech acts that produce effects in the form of actions that will be carried out by the speech partner". These directive speech acts include direct commands as Interviewee 1 stated:

"I tend to use direct commands such as "Please clean your desks" or "Do the following questions honestly" to emphasize instructions to students. However, he also added motivational commands, such as "The better your behavior, the better you will be," as part of an approach that not only directs action but also builds character in students. I think it is important for teachers to deliver commands by considering intonation, facial expressions, and the classroom situation, so that the message is received without giving the impression of being rigidly authoritative. "

Interviewee 1 explained that the use of directive speech acts depends on the situation and conditions of the class. In a conducive class atmosphere, he uses commands with a lower and more relaxed intonation, such as:

"Let's work on the questions in groups," while in certain conditions, such as when students are less disciplined or the classroom environment is dirty, he uses a higher intonation to emphasize the command, for example "Let's try to clean it!"

In addition, Interviewee 1 used direct commands more often than indirect or sarcastic ones, especially for grade 12 students. According to Hadiwijaya et al.²⁰, "the directive speech act of request is a type of speech act that functions to get the speech partner to do something requested by the speaker". Grade 12 students are more mentally prepared to receive direct instructions, while grade 10 students tend to be given directions in a gentler and more persuasive manner.

Interviewee 1 also emphasized that directive speech acts are not only limited to academic tasks, but also include orders as a homeroom teacher which have a broader scope. Larasati et al.²¹ explained that, acts encountered in interactions in educational relationships that are based on conversations between teachers and students in the teaching and learning process. A teacher has the authority to convey or give advice, order, prohibit, invite, ask questions, and give permission to students.

However, in every form of speech act given, he still considers the aspect of politeness by adjusting intonation, word choice, and the context of the interaction in order to continue to build a good relationship with students. Musyawir²² stated that " speech acts must adapt to the situation or context of the utterance". Meanwhile, the results of observations of Interviewee 2, an English teacher, found that the forms of directive speech acts used in communication between teachers and students were diverse, including commands, requests, and suggestions.

"Through directive speech acts, a teacher can utilize forms of directive speech acts such as requests, questions, orders, prohibitions, permission, advice, and others. Each form of speech act has a function in the learning process. Teachers can use forms of speech acts alternately that are adjusted to the function of the utterance that is appropriate to the context." 23

Teachers tend to use indirect forms in delivering instructions in order to maintain politeness in communication, such as with sentence patterns.

"Would you like to...? Which is more polite than a direct command such as "Study reading!"

Politeness in this communication has a big influence on students' responses, where they are more likely to obey instructions with a good attitude. The emotional closeness factor between teachers and students also plays an important role in the effectiveness of directive speech acts. Teachers who are able to build good relationships with students tend to get a more positive response, where students feel more comfortable and motivated to follow the directions given.

The observation result of Interviewee 3 also found that the most frequently used form of directive speech act in communication between teachers and students was orders and suggestions. Interviewee 3 explained that in giving instructions to students, he more often used direct orders with additional politeness elements, such as using the word "please" before giving an order.

This aims to build more effective communication and respect students as individuals who also need to be treated well. In addition, the use of polite language has been shown to increase students' attention and response to the instructions given. In the classroom context, commands that are often used involve mutual agreement, such as:

"Please let's agree" or "please do it together".

Interviewee 4, who is a teacher, stated that the form of directive used is generally in the form of a direct command with an active verb such as:

"Please pay attention" or "I beg your attention."

Furthermore, based on the results of observations with Interviewee 5, a student, it was found that the form of directive speech acts used by teachers in communicating with students varies depending on the character and teaching style of each teacher. In general, teachers who give instructions by starting with the words 'minta bantu' (help me, please) and ending with the greeting 'nak' (kid) are considered more polite and create a more comfortable atmosphere for students.

Observation results of Interviewee 6, a student majoring in Engineering, there are various forms of directive speech acts used in communication between teachers and students. Interviewee 6 revealed that each teacher has a different way of delivering instructions, depending on their generation and habits. Some teachers use firm and straightforward language, while others adapt to the more relaxed communication style of Generation Z. According to Asni et al.²⁴, "Generation Z tends to have a communication style characterized by the use of abbreviations and informal language". Interviewee 6 assessed that basically all forms of direction from teachers still contain politeness, although there are differences in the way they are

delivered. He gave an example that instructions such as "Let's do this problem" felt firm, while directions such as "Le (kid), do your homework" felt more affectionate.

Politeness strategies in speech acts

Based on observations of Interviewee 1, with 34 years of teaching experience, the use of politeness strategies in commands is greatly influenced by the level of understanding and readiness of students. Teachers tend to use direct commands, especially to grade 12 students, who are considered more mentally prepared. However, in certain situations, especially when providing motivation, teachers apply politeness strategies by emphasizing the importance of manners and politeness in everyday life. Politeness in speech acts is also seen in the use of respectful terms such as "mas," "mbak," or "le," which show respect for students.

In addition, the classroom situation factor also influences the form of commands used; in more conducive classes, commands are delivered with a low intonation, while in less disciplined classes, teachers use a higher intonation to assert authority. However, when dealing with impolite students, teachers prefer to take a direct personal approach in order to provide advice more effectively. Thus, the politeness strategy in directive speech acts used by teachers not only functions to convey instructions, but also to build a relationship of mutual respect between teachers and students, while instilling politeness values in everyday communication.

Interviewee 3 also emphasized the importance of maintaining politeness in communication by setting a good example for students. He reprimanded students who used impolite language in a mild manner, and tried to direct them to use formal language, especially in learning situations. Windyaningrum & Sondari²⁵ explained, "politeness is something that must be considered in speaking to speech partners, to provide comfort in communicating, in addition to providing comfort in communicating, it can also create a sense of authority, or respect for speech partners".

In addition, interviewee 5 stated that the use of greetings such as 'nak' (kid) or mentioning students' names is also a strategy in delivering commands. In maintaining politeness, teachers avoid using language that is too firm or dominant, but instead use an introduction before delivering commands, such as "try to pay attention."

According to Interviewee 5, the use of polite language and friendly expressions, such as smiling, makes students more motivated to carry out instructions voluntarily. In contrast, teachers who are stricter or considered "galak (killers)" tend to give instructions directly without using polite words, for example with the expression "Rek (guys), erase the board." However, students still carry out the instructions, although sometimes reluctantly or uncomfortable. Other factors that influence politeness in directive speech acts are intonation, facial expressions, and classroom situations. In relaxed classroom conditions, instructions given in a soft tone are easier to accept, while in a tense atmosphere, instructions given directly and without supportive expressions can feel uncomfortable for students. In addition, in providing corrections to student errors, some teachers immediately state the error without giving appreciation first, which can

make students feel less appreciated. However, there are also teachers who reprimand in a more polite way, such as providing feedback gradually, so that students feel more accepted and motivated to correct their mistakes.

In conveying requests to teachers, students tend to use polite expressions such as "Excuse me, ma'am, can I have a favor...?" to maintain communication ethics. In addition, students often use direct sentences when interacting with peers to avoid misunderstandings, for example in giving instructions regarding class duty duties. Politeness in communication between teachers and students is considered important because it reflects individual character and can affect interpersonal relationships. Teachers also tend to adjust their tone of voice to the classroom situation using a louder voice when the class is noisy and a quieter tone when the atmosphere is conducive.

Factors that influence politeness in directive speech acts

The level of politeness in directive speech acts in communication between teachers and students is influenced by several main factors. The first is the educational background and habits and or character of students. Students' politeness in responding to directive speech acts is greatly influenced by education at home and the social environment. Wardani et al.²⁶ states, Vygotsky's theory emphasizes social, cultural, historical and individual interactions as the key to human development. Students who are accustomed to polite communication at home tend to show higher politeness in interactions at school. Conversely, students who are accustomed to rougher communication patterns tend to pay less attention to politeness norms in language. In addition, each student has a diverse character, where some students are more responsive to firm instructions, while others are more comfortable with a more subtle approach.

The second factor is the situation and condition of the class. The class situation is an important factor in determining the level of politeness in communication. According to Goffman²⁷ communication situations are influenced by the social context that shapes interaction behavior. According to Subagio et al.²⁸, "Communication influences and is influenced by factors such as culture, values, norms, social roles, social structures, and the context in which communication occurs. Social communication involves the application of verbal and non-verbal skills to interact socially. This includes the use of appropriate eye contact, facial expressions, social invitations, requests, joint attention, and body language."

In a conducive and highly disciplined class, teachers tend to use a more relaxed tone, while in a less orderly class, teachers must apply a more assertive intonation to make instructions more effective. Interviewee 1 stated that a higher tone of voice is sometimes necessary to control the class, especially when students are less disciplined. The conducive classroom atmosphere and the culture of politeness that has been formed in the school environment also support the effectiveness of communication between teachers and students. Thus, the use of polite directive speech acts not only facilitates the learning process, but also reflects a positive communication culture.

The next factor is the emotional closeness between teachers and students. According to Alim et al.²⁹, "effective teacher communication includes three main aspects, namely clarity in delivering messages,

empathy in building emotional closeness, and the suitability of communication methods to the characteristics of individual students". Teachers who have close relationships with students tend to find it easier to give instructions without having to use an authoritative tone. Interviewee 2 emphasized that the use of indirect request phrases such as "Can you help me...?" is more effective in building polite communication and is well received by students. Politeness in this communication has a major influence on student responses, where they are more likely to obey instructions with a good attitude. The emotional closeness factor between teachers and students also plays an important role in the effectiveness of directive speech acts. Teachers who are able to build good relationships with students tend to get a more positive response, where students feel more comfortable and motivated to follow the directions given. According to Larasati et al.²¹ "student reactions are the result of directive speech acts whose functions are to invite, order, suggest, request, demand, prohibit, give advice, and give permission.

The teacher becomes a leader in directing the flow through speech during the teaching and learning process."

The fourth factor is the character and communication strategy of the teacher. Each teacher has a different communication style, depending on their teaching experience and personal character. According to Iswari³⁰, "a communication strategy is the best combination of all communication elements starting from the communicator, message, media, recipient to the influence designed to achieve optimal communication goals. Communication also occurs in the learning process. The communicator is the teacher and the communicant are the student". Interviewee 4, an Indonesian language teacher, explained that choosing the right words, using introductory words, and using appropriate pronouns are factors that support politeness in directive speech acts. In addition, from the observation results of Interviewee 3, it was found that the use of politeness in communication is an important aspect in maintaining good relationships between teachers and students. Teachers tend to use direct commands with additional polite words such as "please" to ensure that the command is received and carried out properly. In addition, the difference between the use of polite language and direct instructions without politeness greatly affects student responses. More polite language tends to get better attention and response than commands that are too firm or sudden.

Differences in class level and student maturity can also be factors that influence politeness in directive speech acts. Grade 10 students are more often given instructions in a gentler manner than grade 12 students who are more ready to receive direct instructions. In some situations, even the use of sarcasm by grade 12 teachers can be accepted as a form of communication that is still effective. This is in line with Piaget's cognitive development theory (1958) which states that the level of maturity affects an individual's understanding of communication and the meaning of language. According to Barokah et al.³¹, "Piaget's development phase, teachers can use different methods to achieve each stage of their students' cognitive development."

Other factors are the influence of emotional and time factors. Based on observations of Interviewee 7, a 12th grade student, it was found that the teacher's mood affects the level of politeness in communication.

Teachers are required to be able to create a conducive learning situation so that students can learn in a psychological atmosphere that supports the condition of each student and helps them towards optimal development. A conducive learning atmosphere can only be created if the teacher communicates and is friendly to students. The teacher uses polite language, so as not to threaten the student's face. Teacher communication from good, fluent, and polite language can be used as a model by students³².

In the morning, teachers tend to be more patient and polite, while towards the afternoon, especially when fatigue increases, patience can decrease, causing communication to become more assertive or even emotional. Interviewee 6 also mentioned that in certain conditions, such as when the teacher is tired or the student is in a bad mood, the way instructions are delivered can feel less polite, even though the intention is still positive. The context and situation of communication are also influential factors.

Next is the language and cultural factors in communication. In this school, students use regional languages such as Javanese or Madurese in everyday conversation. However, in the formal school environment, teachers try to direct the use of Indonesian to create more formal and structured communication. Mrs. Hikmah, a religious teacher, emphasized that the use of more formal language in the school context helps differentiate the roles between teachers and students, in accordance with Leech's¹⁰ politeness theory, which emphasizes the importance of tact maxims in social interactions. According to Pratama & Setyawan³³, "politeness of language can be seen from the behavior and use of language, because the language used not only determines cultural characteristics but also determines the way or pattern of thinking of the speaker.

Another factor that influences politeness in directive speech acts is the formal-informal situation in communication. Although a teacher can be close to students, in the context of school, the use of formal language is maintained to differentiate the positions between teachers and students. For example, although students are accustomed to using regional languages such as Madurese or Javanese in everyday conversation, in class situations, they are directed to use Indonesian so that communication is more formal and structured. Interviewee 3 also emphasized the importance of providing examples or role models in communicating, including apologizing if they accidentally use less formal language.

Finally, based on observations of Interviewee 6, one of the main factors which influences the level of politeness in directive speech acts between teachers and students is the generational difference between young teachers and senior teachers. Teachers with different generational backgrounds have diverse communication habits, ranging from a more assertive and straightforward way to a more relaxed way and adapting to the communication style of Gen Z. According to Purnama & Farhannaya³⁴, one way to help Gen Z realize the importance of positive communication is through a good environment because Gen Z will feel safe and comfortable in communicating. The implementation of a good environment in interpersonal communication is by providing a positive attitude and positive feedback between the communicator and the communicant.

Conclusion

The results of the study indicate that directive speech acts between teachers and students vary depending on several factors. In academic and disciplinary contexts, teachers tend to use direct commands to provide clear instructions, such as when directing students to complete assignments. In contrast, indirect commands are more often used to maintain politeness and motivate students, especially in situations that require a persuasive approach. Politeness strategies in communication include the use of personal greetings, polite word choices and intonation adjustments according to the classroom situation. Factors that influence the level of politeness include students' educational background, language habits, classroom conditions, and emotional closeness between teachers and students. The characteristics and communication style of teachers and the maturity of students also play a role in responding to directions. The application of polite directive speech acts not only increases the effectiveness of learning, but also creates a harmonious communication atmosphere, makes students feel appreciated and encourages active participation in learning activities.

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